

HO₂IEV: Heavyweight Ontology Based web Information Extraction technique for visionless users

Ahmad C. Bukhari¹, Abid Ali Fareedi², Yong Gi. Kim¹ (Corresponding Author)

¹Department of Computer Science, Research Institute of Computer Science and Information Communication, Gyeongsang National University Jinju, Kyungnam 660-701, Republic Of Korea

²School of Engineering, Jönköping University P.O.Box 1026 SE-551 11 Jönköping, Sweden
ahmad@gnu.ac.kr, ygikim@gnu.ac.kr

Abstract- As the internet grows rapidly, millions of web pages are being added on a daily basis. The extraction of precise information is becoming more and more difficult as the volume of data on the internet increases. Several search engines and information fetching tools are available on the internet, all of which claim to provide the best crawling facilities. For the most part, these search engines are keyword based. This poses a problem for visually impaired people who want to get the full use from online resources available to other users. Visually impaired users require special aid to get along with any given computer system. Interface and content management are no exception, and special tools are required to facilitate the extraction of relevant information from the internet for visually impaired users. The HO₂IEV (Heavyweight Ontology Based Information Extraction for Visually impaired User) architecture provides a mechanism for highly precise information extraction using heavyweight ontology and built-in vocal command system for visually impaired internet users. Our prototype intelligent system not only integrates and communicates among different tools, such as voice command parsers, domain ontology extractors and short message engines, but also introduces an autonomous mechanism of information extraction (hereafter referred to as IE) using heavyweight ontology. In this paper we designed domain specific heavyweight ontology using OWL (Web Ontology Language) for ontology modeling and PAL (Protégé Axiom Language) for axiom writing. We introduced a novel autonomous mechanism for IE by developing prototype software. A series of experiments were designed for the testing and analysis of the performance of heavyweight ontology in general, and our information extraction prototype specifically.

I. INTRODUCTION AND RELATED PAST RESEARCH

The invention of the internet has profoundly changed our means of communication and information sharing. Easy access to the internet has played a major role in both its own growth and its utility in day to day life. In general, anyone and everyone can design a web page and share it without any approval [1]. When the internet was invented, its vision was to create a virtual world in which human and computer work together while sharing information. Although not explicitly stated, this vision of the internet implied the development of computers with the same ability to understand content as a human. Its continuously unchecked growth derailed its structure from its vision. Due to its gigantic scale and the human ability to process information and make connections,

there was not sufficient impetus to correct the deficiencies in the hardware and software side of the equation regarding relevant and correct information retrieval. Currently one has to work a lot to find correct and relevant information in a short span of time because currently the web is designed for human consumption and does not provide any help for machine interpretation. Computers do not yet have the ability to understand the actual meaning of sentences as humans do. Several techniques were used in the past to make the computers operate intelligently while dealing with information. In [2, 3] web content mining and wrapper induction techniques were discussed to extract and integrate the useful data, information and knowledge from web pages. The two methods most widely used in web content mining are wrapper induction information extraction and automatic information extraction. In wrapper induction technique, we use machine learning techniques to make rules for information extraction. In this technique, the user searches the item from the web page, and the machine learning techniques make rules on the behalf of the extracted items. These rules are used in future to find the information about contents and products. We manually tag the contents of the web pages and the machine learning techniques to make the extraction rule. But to write wrapper classes and keep them updated is a very tough job when you consider the dynamic growth on the internet. Whenever the website contents and structure change, we have to relearn our wrapper and make significant changes according to new structures. The probability of errors occurring in wrappers is also very high [3]. Several software were developed for visually impaired internet users to use for retrieving precise information quickly, but most of them used screen reading techniques such as “*BrookesTalk*” [4]. *BrookesTalk* is one of the tools which give a summary of the page to the user vocally. It uses different voices for different parts of the webpage so that the visually impaired user can understand the architecture of the webpage. With the help of this tool, the user can easily navigate between the web pages and extract information at some level. Its ability to produce different sounds for different parts of the webpage sometime irritates the users. Its design is based on the standard tool for visually impaired “*pwWebSpeak*”. Another approach introduced in [5] aims to facilitate the visually impaired users in website searching and navigation. The functionality most often included in these software packages is as follows: providing guidance for visually impaired users, empowering

visually impaired users and reducing cognitive load. The result of this research developed a prototype called “NavAccess”. In [6] the researcher presented the idea of an intelligent web. The layered architecture of this intelligent web (semantic web) concept would produce a machine with the ability to understand a request and infer possible solutions using web data. The basic theme behind a semantic web is to make the web intelligent so that it can understand and conceive the meaning of data [1] [7]. This would be a powerful technology for assisting visually impaired users who require special consideration in terms of interface and how this impacts their ability to extract information from the web efficiently. In this paper we discussed the extended version of HO₂IEV architecture, the philosophical anatomy of this approach discussed in [8] by our team. The architecture (see fig.1) is a novel approach and ray of hope for visually impaired people. Our proposed heavyweight ontology based on highly precise information extraction architecture for visually impaired users describes a mechanism to extract precise information based on vocal command system as discussed in [9]. The rest of the research work is divided in such fashion in section 2 we

described about proposed architecture. Section 3 and 4 deeply explore the layers of proposal. Section 5 belongs to experiments and results. In Section 6 we gave concluding remarks and suggested about possible future work.

II. HEAVY ONTOLOGY BASED PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE

The proposed HO₂IEV (Ontology based highly precise information extraction for visually impaired user) is a novel architecture which facilitates for extraction of highly precise information from heterogeneous web sources using a vocal command system for exact and timely decision making for the visually impaired users. The HO₂IEV architecture is based on already developed technologies, so little effort is needed to implement it publicly. To enable visually impaired people globally to have the same quality of life as normally healthy citizens is a daunting task. The proposed HO₂IEV architecture consists of three functionality layers named as Remote user interaction layer, IE Kernel layer and precise extraction and transmission layer. Let’s explore each layer one by one.

Fig 1. The Proposed HO₂IEV Architecture

A. The Remote User Interaction Layer (Layer 1)

The remote user interaction layer was specially designed to facilitate the remote visually impaired users. We assumed in our experiment that the visually impaired user had a smart phone with pocket CMU SPHINX-2 [10] installed as an application on it. The user records his/her voice message in pocket CMU SPHINX-2 speech to text conversion mode. The user’s voice will automatically be converted into text, and sent to the central server for further processing. This phenomenon needs a real time continuous speech recognition system (RTCSRS) which should be effective, fast and must be lightweight so that mobile devices can easily use this with low power consumption. For this purpose we chose the pocket CMU SPHINX-2 as it is already tested and analyzed by researchers several times in their experiments. The Pocket

CMU-SPHINX2 is an open source large vocabulary continuous speech recognition system. There are many portable text to speech (TTS) and speech to text (STT) recognition systems available on internet under closed license but most of them are expensive and available without source code. The pocket CMU SPHINX-2 is the first known open source continuous speech recognition system to date. Pocket CMU SPHINX-2 is lightweight, and specially developed for a mobile platform and low processing handheld devices. At the layer 1 level, the visually impaired user records a voice message and the built-in Pocket CMU-SPHINX-2 encodes it into data packets. These data packets are sent to the main server on which the prototype tool is installed for further processing.

III. INFORMATION EXTRACTION KERNEL (Layer 2)

A. The AJAX Based SMS Inbound Panel

There are three serial activities which are performed at the second layer of the information extraction kernel. The visually impaired user's text is received at the SMS Server's In-Bound Panel as shown in figure 2. The user can subscribe to an SMS service or GPRS for sending text messages to a server. Almost all mobile phone operating companies provide such text messaging services for a nominal charge. The text message is received at a specially designed (Asynchronous JavaScript and XML) AJAX based dynamic panel. Figure 3 presents the GUI of our developed prototype intelligent. AJAX is not a technology itself, but is instead a combination of JavaScript and XML. With Ajax, web applications can retrieve data from the server asynchronously in the background without interfering with the display and behaviour of the existing page. In AJAX, the server and client remain in connection with the help of an "XMLHttpRequest" method which is specially developed for seamless communication purposes [11]. As the SMS reaches the inbound panel, it automatically forwards the query SMS to the ontology based focused crawler for further processing. Figure 2 shows that the prototype SMS server module, which is developed with JSP and AJAX for handling incoming and outgoing data traffic.

Fig 2. A Screenshot of Web based Intelligent IE System

A. Modeling Heavyweight Ontology for Ontology Crawler

Ontology is considered a branch of metaphysics which focuses on the study of existence and an explicit specification of shared conceptualization [12]. In ontology we basically focus on concepts (classes) of the domain, their relationships and their properties. Ontology arranges the classes in hierarchical structure, in the form of subclass and super class hierarchy, and also defines which property has constraints on its values. Basically, ontology is developed to share common understanding of the domain knowledge among people and software in order to help us reuse the classes of a domain instead of remodelling them. Ontology is written in a specific

language called OWL (Ontology Writing Language) which is developed by W3C. OWL is specially designed for ontology modelling. Fig 3 is showing a code view of OWL class and constraints. There are many methodologies used in the development of ontologies. In [12] seven-steps ontology development steps were discussed which covers almost every aspect of ontology modelling. These steps are:

1. Determine the domain and scope of the ontology
2. Consider reusing existing ontologies
3. Enumerate important terms in the ontology
4. Define the classes and the class hierarchy
5. Define the properties of classes—slots
6. Define the facets of the slots
7. Create instances

For the construction of the domain model, the number of methodologies that precisely address the ontology development issues in different domains [14] and the construction of the ontology have become both an art and understood engineering processes.

We developed heavyweight ontology for an electronic store. The basic difference between lightweight and heavyweight ontology is that in heavyweight ontology, the ontology is enriched by axioms which produce a deep expressivity level. In the past, experiments based on lightweight ontology produced set of results with limited inferences.

```
<?xml version="1.0"?>
<!DOCTYPE rdf:RDF [
]
<rdf:RDF xmlns="http://www.semanticweb.org/ontologies/2010/11/E-Store.owl#"
  owl:Ontology rdf:about="">
  <!-- Electronic Store HeavyWeight Ontology Model file ALLAB GNU -->
  <!-- http://www.semanticweb.org/ontologies/2010/11/E-Store.owl#accessBookAndMagazine -->
  <owl:ObjectProperty rdf:about=""#accessBookAndMagazine">
    <rdf:type rdf:resource=""#owl:FunctionalProperty"/>
  <!-- http://www.semanticweb.org/ontologies/2010/11/E-Store.owl#Apparel -->
  <!-- http://www.semanticweb.org/ontologies/2010/11/E-Store.owl#Domain_User -->
  <owl:Class rdf:about=""#Domain_User">
    <owl:equivalentClass>
      <owl:Restriction>
        <owl:onProperty rdf:resource=""#selectCountryHotel"/>
        <owl:onClass rdf:resource=""#CountryHotel"/>
        <owl:minQualifiedCardinality rdf:datatype=""#xsd:nonNegativeInteger">1</owl:minQualifiedCardinality>
      </owl:Restriction>
    </owl:equivalentClass>
    <owl:equivalentClass>
      <owl:Restriction>
        <owl:onProperty rdf:resource=""#bookingRoom"/>
        <owl:onClass rdf:resource=""#Room"/>
        <owl:minQualifiedCardinality rdf:datatype=""#xsd:nonNegativeInteger">1</owl:minQualifiedCardinality>
      </owl:Restriction>
    </owl:equivalentClass>
    <owl:Restriction>
      <owl:onProperty rdf:resource=""#accessStoreThing"/>
      <owl:onClass rdf:resource=""#E_Store_Thing"/>
      <owl:minQualifiedCardinality rdf:datatype=""#xsd:nonNegativeInteger">1</owl:minQualifiedCardinality>
    </owl:Restriction>
    </owl:equivalentClass>
    </owl:equivalentClass>
    <owl:Restriction>
      <owl:onProperty rdf:resource=""#selectGeographicLocation"/>
      <owl:someValuesFrom rdf:resource=""#GeographicLocation"/>
    </owl:Restriction>
    </owl:equivalentClass>
    </owl:equivalentClass>
    <owl:Class>
      <owl:unionOf rdf:parseType=""#Collection">
        <rdf:Description rdf:about=""#Blind_User"/>
        <rdf:Description rdf:about=""#Female"/>
        <rdf:Description rdf:about=""#Male"/>
      </owl:unionOf>
    </owl:Class>
  </owl:Class>

```

Fig 3. A Snippet of Electronic Store Ontology (E-Store) class

PAL (Protégé Axiom Language) is used to write axioms in

Protégé (a well known ontology development tool by Stanford university) [3]. PAL is basically a constraint language that is used to enforce the semantic properties of knowledge bases encoded in Protégé [11]. These axioms are based on mathematical notation. They add constraints and link the information with other sets of information by applying certain criteria. The addition of axioms in lightweight ontology increases the expressivity level of ontology, and helps in machine interpretability. We modelled a light weight ontology first, then added axioms to achieve deeper expressivity level. In PAL, constraints include a set of variables, which are range definitions and logical statements. Predefined predicates and functions create a statement. Logical connectives (\Leftrightarrow , \Rightarrow) (*if*, *and*, *or*) are used to link up ontology and other predefined predicates. The PAL constraints for the electronic store ontology in which an *IPhone* price must be greater than *Nokia3200* can be coded as shown in fig 4.

```
(defrange ?IPhone :FRAME IPHONE )
(defrange ?Nokia3200:FRAME Nokia3200 responsible_for)(forall
? IPHONE (forall ? Nokia3200
( $\Rightarrow$  (and (responsible_for ? IPHONE ? Nokia3200)
(own-slot-not-null Price? IPHONE )
(own-slot-not-null Price? Nokia3200))
( $>$  (Price? IPHONE ) (Price? Nokia3200))))))
```

Fig 4. The PAL axioms Code File

IPhone is the name of the variable. Variable names start either with ‘?’ or ‘%’ which define local and global variables, respectively. FRAME is one type of variable. Other types of variables are SET, SYMBOL, STRING, INTEGER, and NUMBER. Fig. 5 shows the inferred model of the E-Store ontology. The inferred model is the graphical structure of interconnected domain elements. We used *Pellet Reasoner* Tool in Protégé to generate inferences; A screen view of *Palett Rasoner* can be seen in fig 6(a). This domain ontology is used as input in our ontology crawler and the ontology crawler (see fig 6(b) for ontology crawler) populates the corpus from the internet. The entire website which falls under ontology defined rules is considered as the part of the corpus. Our designed prototype will automatically receive short message and convert them into description logic queries (dl-queries). The resulting queries will fetch the information from the corpus. This information is not in natural language, requiring a natural language processing API to interpret the resulting query in order to make the results understandable to the user [14].

III. THE PRECISE EXTRACTOR AND TRANSMISSION LAYER(LAYER 3)

Relevant information extraction from the web is always a difficult process in the information engineering domain. A web crawler is a program that browses the web automatically. The difference between a simple web crawler and a focused web crawler is that a simpler crawler just searches the web and indexes the results which may be relevant or not. The focused crawler only indexes pages which belong to a particular

domain, and which converge with certain predefined criteria [16]. Many web crawlers developed in the past had different criteria for searching based on page relevance, link relevance and so on. The server side dynamic web pages are based on databases, and these web page contents are populated in real time from the database and the populated values from the database changes according to the defined criteria. Therefore, the crawler which indexes the web pages on the behalf of page and link relevance fails at this stage. To overcome this problem, ontology based crawlers are used at layer 2 level which extract the precise information from web. The proposed HO₂IEV architecture at the third layer utilizes the GATE API which indexes the relevant web information from the scattered data on the internet. The internal ontology based web crawler first fetches the web pages from the web with its fetcher component and the information is then parsed. The data is stored in the local cache followed by the ontology techniques which are applied against the fetched web pages. Only the most relevant web pages are indexed. We used the open source ontology authoring tool Protégé 4.0.2 [16] [17] to develop the electronic store ontology. The e-store ontology defines the classes, subclasses and most of the properties of the electronic store domain. In figure 2 we suppose a user sends a query from voice user interface to AJAX based query panel after processing from CMU. Pocket Sphinx mechanism then converts the speech into text. The AJAX based panel automatically routes the query to the ontology based focused crawler which is loaded with our developed electronic store ontology. The ontology based crawler starts its operation and the results are indexed as to which results meet the ontology criteria. At last stage of layer 3, the prototype sends extracted information to outbound panel which further transmit it to user.

Fig 5. E-Store heavyweight ontology inferred Model generated by Protégé OWL-VIZ extension

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

A. Research Design Evaluation and Validity

To ensure the effectiveness of our research design in ontology based information systems we have some known ways of evaluation, such as description logic queries, user level testing and domain expert manual evaluation. DL-Query is a powerful and user friendly tool used for searching a classified ontology. We tested and analyzed the performance of our modeled ontology using Protégé 4.0. Manchester OWL syntax is used for writing description logic queries. ‘Reasoner’ must be executed before applying any query. ‘Reasoner’ is basically a tool which can infer information on the basis of described rules. The Protégé Package normally has ‘FACT++’ and ‘Pellet’ as reasoner by default. We used ‘Pellet’ reasoner in our experiment. Pellet is one of the best tools which provide cutting edge reasoning for sound and complete information extraction. Pellet is available in the Protégé Package by default, or it can be added as a third party utility. Figure 6 shows the Pellet is working on electronic store ontology.

Fig 6. Pelett Reasoner in working mode

We designed some queries (with user and domain expert concern) to completely judge the overall performance of the system and found result according to requirement. Some of these are listed in table 1 and resulting screenshots can be viewed in 6(c) and 6(d).

TABLE 1. DL-QUERIES WITH POSSIBLE RESULTS

DL-Query Syntax	Explanation	Possible Results
<i>Travel_Agency</i> and <i>bookHotelReservation value</i> <i>HotelReservationI</i>	In this query the domain user wants information from a travel agency, whose schedule is selected according to the domain user’s schedule. Information selection depends on whether or not the travel agency has any travel packages for trains, cruises and airlines. Figure shows the result of the query.	Swedish Travel Agency

<i>Travel_Agency</i> and <i>bookHotelReservation value</i> <i>HotelReservationI</i>	This query displays travel agencies that can make hotel reservations.	XANADU and Swedish
<i>Domain_User</i> and <i>accessJewelry value</i> <i>BraceletJewelryI</i>	This query describes the user, who, for the purposes of our test, is the valid domain user and likes jewelry; specifically, bracelets.	Blind Female User

A. System Precision Measurements

A series of experiments were designed to test and evaluate the efficiency and performance of the ontology, and the performance and information extraction capabilities of the prototype tool. Normally in every information extraction system there are three main performance measures: extraction rate, precision and recall. These parameters are considered while evaluating the performance of the system. Mathematically precision and recall can be expressed as:

$$RC = \frac{ce}{ce + te} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

$$PR = \frac{ce}{ce + fe} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

Where RC is the recall and PR is the precision ‘ce’ is the correct information that is extracted, ‘te’ and ‘fe’ represents the right and wrong information that are extracted by system respectively. Our experimental environment had Intel(R) Core (TM) 2 Quad CPU with 2.0 GB RAM, Window XP. We used Tomcat as web server and CDMA based external modem for sending and receiving user SMS. First, we designed the lightweight ontology and loaded it into our ontology crawler. Then we added the axioms into our ontology and refined it to get deep expressivity levels. After that, we loaded the ontology into the crawler and searched from the internet. The lightweight ontology was loaded first and then checked. After we completed gathering our results, we loaded the heavyweight ontology and checked that. We obtained different precision and recall results, shown in the tables below. Table 2 and 3 depict some statistics of ontology base information extraction crawler. We have noted that precision and recall ratios using a conventional ontology approach are:

TABLE 2. PRECISION AND RECALL STATISTICS OF PROTOTYPE SYSTEM USING LIGHTWEIGHT ONTOLOGY

Ontology Elements	Resource Elements (ce)	True Elements (te)	False Elements (fe)	Precision (PR) (%)	Recall (RC) (%)
<i>Class(Concept)</i>	413	235	178	69.9	63.7
<i>Property</i>	687	496	191	77.3	58.1
<i>Individual</i>	109	78	31	77.9	52.3

TABLE 3. PRECISION AND RECALL STATISTICS OF PROTOTYPE SYSTEM USING HEIVYWEIGHT ONTOLOGY

Ontology Elements	Resource Elements (ce)	True Elements (te)	False Elements (fe)	Precision (PR) (%)	Recall (RC) (%)
Class(Concept)	413	389	24	94.5	51.5
Property	687	591	96	87.8	53.8
Individual	109	93	16	87.2	54.0

69.9%, 77.3%, 77.9% and 63.7%, 58.1%, 52.3% respectively. In the case of the heavyweight ontology, the precision rate increased from 69.9% to 94.5%, 77.3% to 87.8% and 77.9% to 87.2%. So according to our experiment more precise information can be achieved by using heavyweight ontology.

Fig 7. Graphical comparison between lightweight and heavyweight ontology

In figure 10, the bar graph shows a comparison between heavyweight and lightweight ontologies on the basis of true and false elements. On the y-axis, the metric 0 to 700 refers to elements retrieved by the ontology crawler's spider. "Classes," "Property" and "Individual" on the x-axis refer to the measurement of the classification of results.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this research paper, we propose precise information extraction architecture for visually impaired computer users using ontology based highly for several compelling reasons. The automatic execution of this novel architecture makes it faster and more adaptable than existing solutions. The interactivity of the prototype enables the user to retrieve and filter the desired information while roaming. The classical wrapper writing exercise is time consuming as it needs to be continuously upgraded. Once the domain ontology is developed, it does not need any continuous updating. We presented the results and performance measures of our tool and ontology. The results were dramatically better than our previous experiments. The enrichment of axioms produces a quality of expressivity, and makes the information more understandable for computers. As a result, the precision of extracted information increases. Currently, we are developing

new capabilities for automatic axioms rules generation, and improving the portability of this system. More research is required, but we are confident that this will make the system more efficient overall.

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